

IS IT POSSIBLE TO ELIMINATE MICRO-SCALE STRESS CONCENTRATIONS IN COMPOSITES BY NANO ENGINEERING WITH CNTS?

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ABSTRACT

A spatial distribution of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in fiber-reinforced composites is investigated to suppress stress concentrations at the micro-scale. Two types of CNT networks are modelled. The first one consists of CNTs located directly in the areas of high stresses to be eliminated. In the second network, a long range effect of CNTs is exploited. The results indicate that one can, indeed, suppress stresses in the matrix through introduction of CNT networks and this can be done without affecting stresses in the rest of the matrix. The alignment of CNTs is found to play an important role in achieving this effect. A nearly complete elimination of microscopic inter-fiber stress concentrations can be realized.

1. Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) introduced in a fiber reinforced composite (FRC) have a strong influence on the stress state of the matrix at the micro-scale. From our previous numerical studies [1-3] using finite element (FE) modeling we know that due to the presence of CNTs stresses in the matrix between fibers become highly heterogeneous. The stress disturbance is governed by the morphology of the introduced CNT network. Numerical experiments show that conventional strategies for the introduction of CNTs in FRCs, such as CNT dispersion in the matrix or CNT growth on the fibers, can be effective in suppressing stress concentrations in certain matrix regions. At the same time, however, stresses tend to increase in other matrix zones. In [3], we showed that it is possible to suppress matrix stresses in desired areas without increasing stress levels in the rest of the matrix. It was achieved by selective reinforcement of certain matrix zones in which high stress concentrations were anticipated. In the present study, this effect is further investigated.

The target zones for stress suppression are microscopic stress concentrations in the narrow inter fiber spacing as shown in Figure 1a. These stress concentrations (to be referred as “ μ SCs”) are shown for the case of the biaxial tension on a UD FRC unit cell. An ideal case scenario is illustrated in Figure 1b, where the elimination of μ SCs is achieved with no compromise of stresses in the rest of the matrix. By suppressing the stress concentrations, the stress distribution in the matrix would become quasi-uniform. This is expected to change the damage onset mechanism that is based on the analysis of micro-scale stress concentrations in the matrix.

Figure 1. Maximum principal stresses in matrix under biaxial tensile loading (a) with and (b) without microscopic stress concentrations between the fibers. (a) is an actual stress distribution in a composite with homogeneous matrix, while (b) is a targeted stress distribution with a nano-engineered network in the matrix.

2. Procedure for generation of CNT networks

Only strongly oriented and aligned CNT networks are expected to effectively suppress stresses. For this purpose, the CNT reinforced “bridges” between the fibers are introduced into the model. Two types of CNT bridges are considered. The first type is quasi-straight aligned CNTs located directly in zones of high stresses between the fibers. The second type is quasi-aligned CNTs localized around these zones. The study is performed on an example of a random periodic arrangement of fibers subjected to biaxial tension. The fiber arrangement is obtained using the Random Microstructure Generation algorithm described and characterized in [4].

Figure 2. CNT “bridges” generation procedure: (a) creating the Voronoy diagram for fiber distribution; (b) selecting neighboring fibers with a minimum distance criterion; (c) determining zones for “direct bridges” linking these neighboring fibers and cutting these zones into the RVE; (d)

generating aligned CNTs inside the “direct bridge” zones; (e) determining zones for “arc bridges” by linking neighboring fibers; (f) generating aligned CNTs inside these “arc bridge” zones.

i. “Direct CNT bridges”

Referred as a “direct bridge” further in the text, the first type of CNT bridges is quasi-straight aligned CNTs located directly in a zone of high stresses. Performed in Matlab, the following procedure of the “direct bridge” generation is schematically shown in Figure 2.

First, for the fiber arrangement obtained from the RMG algorithm, the Voronoy diagram is constructed defining neighboring fibers (Figure 2a). Then, those neighboring fibers, that are at the distance less than R , are distinguished and lines connecting their centers are drawn. These are to be referred as “bridge-lines” (Figure 2b). Then, along the bridge-lines, the rectangular zones are assigned having width d_b , equal to $1.5 \mu\text{m}$, and connecting the corresponding fiber surfaces (marked with dark grey on Figure 2c). Being cut by the unit cell boundaries, these zones are to be referred as “bridge zones”. After that, in each of these zones, CNTs are generated.

Figure 3. Schematics of the CNT generation procedure for the “direct CNT bridge” (top) and the “arc CNT bridge” (bottom).

The procedure for CNT generation in “direct bridges” is schematically shown in Figure 3 (top). The first vertex is randomly positioned inside the bridge zone and each following vertex-to-vertex line is allowed to deviate by not more than $\beta = 10^\circ$ from the direction parallel to the bridge-line. If during this procedure, the CNT “meets” a fiber, it continues to grow from its other end. By this procedure, quasi-straight CNTs aligned with the bridge-line are generated forming a “direct bridge” between the fibers.

ii. “Arc CNT bridges”

Another way to position CNTs is around the zone of high stresses. This type of a CNT bridge will be called an “arc bridge”. The procedure for its generation is schematically shown in Figure 2. The first two steps are the same as for the “direct bridges”: the Voronoy diagram is constructed (Figure 2a) and the bridge-lines between the close neighbor fibers are drawn (Figure 2b). Then, as shown in Figure 3, the arc is drawn having its end points at the centers of the adjacent fibers and its farthest point at a distance of $d_b / 2$ from the bridge line. This arc-line is to be referred as a “bridge-

arc”. Its radius, R_{arc} , is calculated proportionally to the distance between the given neighbor fibers. Having the same center with the first arc, the second arc with a radius of $R_{arc} + d_b/2$ is drawn. The resulting hoop zones in between these arcs are “arc zones” (marked with dark grey on Figure 2e). After that, within each arc zone, CNTs are generated.

The procedure for CNT generation in an “arc bridge” is schematically shown in Figure 3 (bottom). The first vertex is randomly thrown into an arc zone. Other vertices are randomly generated in such a way that the distance between them and the bridge-arc stays approximately the same. In the XY-plane, the orientation deviation of vertex-to-vertex lines is set to be not more than $\alpha = 10^\circ$ from the direction parallel to the bridge-arc. In the z-direction, the orientation deviation of vertex-to-vertex lines from the XY-plane is also set to be not more than $\alpha = 10^\circ$.

In both types of bridges, each individual CNT is based on eight vertices. All CNTs have a length of $0.6 \mu\text{m}$ and a radius, R_{CNT} , of 4.5 nm . This corresponds to the number of segments per micron of CNT length, P_{segm} , of 11.7 and L_{segm} of $0.086 \mu\text{m}$. In every model, CNTs are distributed among the bridges such that the CNT packing density in each bridge is the same.

3. Model description

As a unit cell, a random periodic arrangement of 11 fibers with radius $R = 3.5 \mu\text{m}$ and volume fraction of 50% is considered (Figure 4). The unit cell is subjected to periodic boundary conditions (PBCs) simulating the biaxial tension equivalent to strain of 0.3% in x and y directions and zero-displacement in z direction.

Figure 4. A 3D unit cell of a UD carbon fiber composite with two types of CNT bridges: (a) “direct CNT bridges”; (b) “arc CNT bridges”. The right column shows a zoom-in view on the CNT bridge. The cases of 745 CNT are shown.

For the case of “direct bridges”, in total, 745 CNTs are generated which corresponds to the CNT weight fraction to the matrix of 0.05% and to a local CNT weight fraction in the bridge zones of 0.45%. For the case of “arc bridges”, two models are created with 745 CNTs and 1510 CNTs in total which correspond to a global CNT weight fraction of 0.05% and 0.1%, respectively, and to the local CNT weight fraction in the arc zones of nearly 0.45% and 0.9%, respectively.

Perfect contact between all entities and elastic behavior of all materials are assumed. The epoxy matrix is modelled with Young’s modulus $E_m=3$ GPa and Poisson ratio $\nu_m=0.4$. Carbon fibers are modeled as transversely isotropic with $E_{f1}=276$ GPa, $E_{f2}=E_{f3}=10.3$ GPa, $G_{f23}=3.8$ GPa, $G_{f13}=27.9$ GPa, $\nu_{f13}=0.26$, where “1” is the fiber direction. CNTs are modeled with Young’s modulus $E_{CNT}=475$ GPa and Poisson’s ratio $\nu_{CNT}=0.3$. In all four models, the matrix element size is set as $13.8 \cdot R_{CNT}$. The model with 1510 CNT is meshed with the same element size, since the area of interest for the stress analysis in the present study lies away from the arc zones. CNT elements size is $4 \cdot R_{CNT}$.

4. Results and discussion

Figure 5 shows contour plots of the maximum principal stress, σ_I , calculated in the matrix for the reference composite without CNTs and the composites with the CNT bridges. The contour plots are taken at the central cross-section of the unit cell in z-direction. The color scales are set the same for all three configurations in order to allow comparison. The dark red and dark blue colors represent higher and lower stresses, respectively, beyond the extremes of the color scheme.

Figure 5. Contour plots of σ_I stress in the matrix for the reference composite without CNTs; the composite with “direct bridges” with 745 CNTs; and the composites with “arc bridges” with 745 CNTs and 1510 CNTs.

It is seen that microscopic stress concentrations (μ SCs) in the narrow zones in-between closely positioned fibers, are affected in every CNT-bridge scenario. In case of “direct CNT bridges”, μ SCs are effectively suppressed. In the bridge zones, nearly aligned to the direction of σ_I stresses, CNTs directly reinforce the matrix and suppress σ_I stresses the same way as aligned CNT forests grown on fibers suppress the fiber/matrix interface stresses (see [1, 2]). However, in contrast to the CNT forests, CNTs in bridges are not attached to the fibers. Aligned nearly perpendicular to the fiber surface, these CNTs are allowed to be at a certain distance from the latter generating local stress concentrations between the CNTs and the fiber surface. Occurring locally at the CNT tips but merging together along the bridge width, these nano-scale stress concentrations might become a micro-scale high stress event at the fiber/matrix interface.

Both models of “arc CNT bridges” show similar effect within the arc zones as in the case of “direct bridges”: in these matrix areas, the stresses are effectively suppressed. Being oriented parallel to cylindrical areas of a large radius (R_{arc} varies in between 10.4 μ m and 13.8 μ m); CNTs in “arc bridges” are also oriented nearly towards the direction of σ_I stresses, thus being effective in the suppression of the latter. However, the effect of “arc bridges” on the μ SCs is more difficult to predict as for them to be effective an additional optimization of their shape and CNT density are required. The reason lies in the different stress suppression principle. Unlike the “direct bridges”, the “arc bridges” do not directly reinforce the high stress zones. Instead, CNTs are located close to these zones and affect them through long distance interactions. Although, the suppression effect on μ SCs is distinguishable and becomes stronger with higher concentration of CNTs, it does not reach the level of stress suppression caused by the “direct CNT bridges”. Further optimization of the network morphology is needed to understand the potential of this approach.

For the quantitative analysis, the profiles of σ_I stress along the bridge-lines that are attached to the central fibers are investigated (Figure 6). Marked with Roman numerals in Figure 6, central fibers are the ones that are fully within the unit cell. Marked with Arabic numerals in Figure 6, the bridge-lines are processed sequentially: stress is calculated in matrix elements closest to these and averaged through the thickness of the model. Then, the obtained average σ_I stress values are normalized to the reference value σ_I^{ref} corresponding to the composite with no CNTs:

$$\bar{\sigma}_I = \frac{\sigma_I}{\sigma_I^{ref}} \tag{1}$$

Figure 6. Central fiber and bridge indexing.

The normalized bridge-line length \bar{x} can be defined as the distance along the bridge-line divided by bridge-line length. Plots with the profiles of $\bar{\sigma}_I(\bar{x})$ are gathered in Figure 7. In each plot, the reference curve is represented by a constant value. It is seen that all curves corresponding to the “arc

bridges” lie slightly below the reference. The case of 1510 CNTs provides a more effective stress suppression along the bridge-lines. However, the stress suppression, $\delta\bar{\sigma}_l$, barely reaches 1.9% and 3.8% for the “arc bridges” with 745 CNTs and 1510 CNTs, respectively. The average stress suppression, $\langle \delta\bar{\sigma}_l \rangle$, is 1.2% and 2.3%. The “direct bridges”, on the other hand, reduce $\bar{\sigma}_l$ stresses up to 11.6%. The average stress reduction by “direct bridges” is about 5.3%. The corresponding data for $\bar{\sigma}_l$ characterization is gathered in Table 1.

The stress suppression effect can also be characterized by means of stress moderation towards the matrix stress state in the absence of μ SCs. In other words, how low the resulted stress along the bridge-lines becomes with the respect to the major low stress in the rest of the matrix, away from μ SCs. Referred further in the text as σ_m , such stress is taken as the average σ_l stress calculated in the matrix except for the bridge zones in the reference composite without CNTs. This value is the same for all the models and is equal to 39.6 MPa. Marked with the light green color in Figure 5, it is the middle of the stress scatter presented in the contour plots.

Figure 7. The profiles of $\bar{\sigma}_l$ stress in each of the ten considered bridges for the composite with the “arc bridges” (745 CNTs and 1510 CNTs); with the “direct CNT bridges” (745 CNTs); and without CNTs.

In order to estimate the stress suppression with respect to σ_m , the following stress normalization is performed:

$$\bar{\sigma}_I' = \frac{\sigma_I - \sigma_m}{\sigma_I^{ref} - \sigma_m} \quad (2)$$

Calculated using Eq.4.2, the normalized values for the composite with no CNTs, $\bar{\sigma}_I^{ref}$, are equal to 1. When it reaches 0 value, $\bar{\sigma}_I'$ signifies σ_I approaching to σ_m value; in other words, approaching the effective suppression of μ SCs to the state of elimination of the latter. This corresponds to a $\bar{\sigma}_I'$ decrease value, $\delta\bar{\sigma}_I'$, of 100%.

Figure 8. The profiles of $\bar{\sigma}_I'$ stress in each of ten considered bridges for the composite with the “arc bridges” (745 CNTs and 1510 CNTs); with the “direct CNT bridges” (745 CNTs); and without CNTs.

All ten plots with the profiles of $\bar{\sigma}_I'(\bar{x})$ are gathered in Figure 8. The corresponding data for $\bar{\sigma}_I'$ characterization is gathered in Table 1. The curves are similar to the $\bar{\sigma}_I$ profiles shown in Figure 7; however, the $\bar{\sigma}_I'$ profiles provide a better qualitative estimation of the stress suppression.

	$max \delta \bar{\sigma}_l$	$< \delta \bar{\sigma}_l >$	$max \delta \bar{\sigma}_l'$	$< \delta \bar{\sigma}_l' >$
“arc bridges”, 745 CNTs	1.9%	1.2%	43.7%	16.9%
“arc bridges”, 1510 CNTs	3.8%	2.3%	86.5%	32.2%
“direct bridges”, 745 CNTs	11.6%	5.3%	214.6%	64.4%

Table 1. $\bar{\sigma}_l$ and $\bar{\sigma}_l'$ characterization data.

For instance, in case of the “arc bridges” with 745 CNTs, the $\bar{\sigma}_l'$ values are reduced up to 43.7%, which means that σ_l stresses along the bridge-lines become closer to σ_m value up to 43.7%. Yet, the average $\bar{\sigma}_l'$ decrease, $< \delta \bar{\sigma}_l' >$, is smaller – 16.9%, which indicates a 16.9% average mitigation of σ_l stresses towards σ_m value. For the case of 1510 CNTs, the maximum $\bar{\sigma}_l'$ values reduction, $max \delta \bar{\sigma}_l'$, is 86.5%; $< \delta \bar{\sigma}_l' > = 32.2\%$.

The “direct CNT bridges” show very effective σ_l stress suppression. With $max \delta \bar{\sigma}_l'$ of 214.6%, this type of CNT bridges provide σ_l stresses values significantly lower than σ_m , which indicates the “over-suppression” of σ_l stresses with the respect to the average stress in the rest of the matrix. The corresponding $< \delta \bar{\sigma}_l' >$ value is 64.4%, which is 3.8 times higher than for the “arc bridges” with the same number of CNTs – 745.

The reader should note that the CNT configurations presented here are not completely optimized. Reaching the main goal of μ SCs suppression, they still cause some local stress concentrations within the bridge zones. In addition, only one type of the applied load was considered in the present study. Clearly, in order to effectively suppress μ SCs in the case of uniaxial or shear load, different architecture of CNT reinforcement interdependent with the fiber positions should be established. To address these issues, further optimization of the CNT configurations is needed.

5. On the practical realization of intelligent CNT structures

Yet, one of the main remaining challenges is the practical realization of such complex CNT arrangements. So far, materials scientists did not approach the techniques that could make it achievable. However, in recent years, the understanding and control of nanoparticle assemblies have received significant attention.

Significant efforts have been put into understanding and developing the principles for directed self-assemblies (DSAs) of nano-particles [5, 6]. Electric or magnetic field driven control of nano-particles DSAs has received significant attention in literature [7-9]. Another example of self-assembled CNT microstructures is double-helix CNT bundles [10-14] that are synthesized by the chemical vapor deposition (CVD) process. None of the mentioned techniques can be directly applied to address the present problem of the CNT bridges. However, they give a perspective on the research direction towards realization of very complex hierarchical nano-/micro-structures.

A hypothetical, yet, possible way of practical realization of aligned CNT bridges constructed interdependently with the fiber positions in FRC is presented in Figure 9 and could be executed as follows. First, the fibers in a dry carbon UD layer are covered with a catalyst layer (Figure 9a). Then, under the high pressure, the fibers are forced to pack closely to each other. After that, keeping the transverse compression of fibers, a chemical solvent is flown for a limited time through the UD layer in longitudinal direction dissolving the catalyst and washing it off from the open fiber surfaces (Figure 9b). Because of the limited time wherein this step is executed, the catalyst on the fibers is not dissolved completely. The applied transverse pressure and friction forces do not allow the remaining catalyst particles to be washed out completely from the fiber surfaces. By this, on each fiber, the catalyst would remain only on those zones of fiber surface that are close to the touching areas with the adjacent fibers. Then, the applied pressure is relieved.

After that, using the CVD process, CNTs are grown from the remaining catalyst zones (Figure 9c); grown CNTs link the close fibers together. Due to strong van der Waals forces, CNTs from the adjacent forests interact with each other and form bundles. The latter is a quite common effect that occurs during growth of CNT forests on closely located fibers [15]. Then, the UD layer locally grafted with CNTs is stretched in the directions perpendicular to the fiber axes pulling the fibers away from each other (Figure 9c). Being interacted with neighbor CNT forests, the stretched grown CNTs become aligned perpendicular to the adjacent fibers (Figure 9d).

According to [16], after stretching with a strain of 40%, the networks of randomly oriented and curved CNTs obtain a fraction of aligned nanotubes up to 85%. Thus, in the bridge problem, in order to obtain final fiber volume fraction of 50% after biaxial strain of 0.4, the initial volume fraction should be around 58% (calculated for hexagonal fiber packing). After stretching, CNTs would be straightened and more closely packed.

Finally, the resin is infused in the direction transverse to fibers since the preferred wetting route lies along CNT axes [17]. After the curing process, the FRCs with aligned CNT bridges in between the neighbor fibers is obtained.

Figure 9. Aligned CNT bridges practical realization proposal. (a) compressed dry fabrics covered with catalyst; (b) chemical solvent infusion in fiber direction to dissolve and wash extra-catalyst out; (c) CNT growth on the remained catalyst followed by grafted fabrics biaxial stretching prior to resin infusion; (d) straightened and more closely packed CNTs forming aligned CNT bridges between neighbor fibers.

Of course, this is just a schematically introduced idea of possible practical realization of the aligned CNT bridge structures. The provided procedure does not cover many issues and problems

associated with the chosen material processing techniques. The actual realization of such intelligent CNT configurations within the hierarchy of FRCs might be significantly more difficult.

6. Conclusions

In this study, the potential of CNT networks for the matrix stress suppression in desired areas avoiding stress magnification in the rest of the matrix is investigated. The following conclusions were underlined:

- Spatial distribution of CNTs can be used to suppress stress concentrations in FRCs at the micro-scale without affecting stresses in the rest of the matrix. The location of CNTs directly in the areas of high stresses is an effective way to suppress the latter. The CNT alignment plays an important role in this suppression. The location of CNTs closely around the high stresses zone also has a mitigation effect, however, less pronounced. It was shown that such remote reinforcement has a potential to indirectly suppress stresses in the zone between the fibers.
- The configuration of CNT bridges for the effective suppression of microscopic stress concentrations is dependent on the direction of the applied load. Therefore, optimization studies on the appropriate structure of CNT networks interdependent with the fiber positions are needed.
- Most importantly, by intelligently constructed CNT networks, it is possible to control stress distribution in heterogeneous materials influencing the mechanisms of the damage initiation.

Yet, one of the main remaining challenges is the practical realization of such complex CNT arrangements. However, the modeling results presented in this paper might be that first step to define a vector for the future practical realization of the intelligent CNT networks for suppression of the micro-scale stress concentrations.

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